

Isoquinoline Derivatives : Part XX. Synthesis of Ethyl 1-Bromo-3-Amino-*isoquinoline*-4-Butyrate and Ethyl 3-Carbethoxy-1, 2-Dihydro*isoquinoline*-4-Butyrate

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In order to build up azasteroid skeleton, two intermediate *isoquinolinyl* ester derivatives have been synthesised.

With an object to synthesise some newer azasteroids of pharmacological importance some intermediate *isoquinoline* derivatives were required. This communication deals with the synthesis of two newer *isoquinolines* of structure III and VI by the following routes :

o-Cyanobenzylcyanide¹ (I) has been alkylated with ethyl γ -bromobutyrate in presence of potassium tertiary butoxide following the method of Johnson and Nasutavicus² to afford the dinitrile compound (II) which on cyclisation with hydrobromic acid has yielded Ethyl 1-bromo-3-amino-*isoquinoline*-4-butyrate (III). Ethyl γ -bromobutyrate has been prepared from γ -bromobutyric acid, which is obtained by the action of hydrobromic acid on trimethylene cyanohydrin³. The cyclisation of the dinitrile compound (II), in the present case,

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1. S. Gabriel and R. Otto, *Ber.*, 1887, **20**, 2222.
2. F. Johnson and W. A. Nasutavicus, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, **27**, 3953.
3. S. Sandrin, E. Cherbuliez, H. Probst and J. Rabinowitz, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1958, **41**, 1163.

has yielded only one *isoquinoline* derivative (III), which is in accordance with the observation of Johnson and Nasutavicus². Parallel to the observation of Johnson and Nasutavicus², another seven membered aza heterocyclic ring fused with the *isoquinoline* system, which was likely to be formed along with (III), however, could not be isolated in the present case.

The chloro compound of β -ketopimelate (IV) has been condensed with benzylamine and the resultant product (V) has been cyclised with sulphuric acid at 0° to yield Ethyl 3-carbethoxy-1,2-dihydro*isoquinoline*-4-butyrate (VI).

Further work in this line is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

γ -Bromo-butyric acid : Trimethylene cyanohydrin³ (82 g.) was mixed with hydrobromic acid (48%; 350 ml.) and the mixture was heated to brisk refluxing in an oil bath at 140° for 6 hr. The excess hydrobromic acid was then removed by distillation under reduced pressure. The liquid product thus left was treated with carbon tetrachloride (150 ml.), filtered and the carbon tetrachloride layer separated. The aqueous layer from above was further extracted with carbon tetrachloride and the combined carbon tetrachloride layer was made anhydrous with calcium chloride. The solvent was then removed by repeated fractionation with an efficient column. The remaining liquid was distilled under vacuum and the fraction boiling between 128–130°/8–10 mm (Lit⁴ b.p. 127°/7 mm.) was collected which sets solid on cooling in freezing mixture, m.p. 32–33° (Lit⁵ m.p. 33°). Yield 39 g.

Ethyl γ -bromobutyrate : A mixture of γ -bromobutyric acid (39 g.) in carbontetrachloride (400 ml), ethyl alcohol (125 ml) and hydrobromic acid (9.5 ml) was heated under reflux for 4 hr. in a Dean and Stark apparatus until the separation of water formed during the course of reaction was complete. The reaction mixture was then cooled, washed successively with dilute sodium carbonate solution and water, and then distilled using an efficient fractionating column to remove excess of the solvent. The residual liquid was then distilled from a fractionating claisen flask under vacuum and the fraction boiling between 103–104°/28–30 mm (Lit⁶ b.p. 104–5°/28 mm; Lit⁷ b.p. 83–84°/13 mm) was collected. Yield 52 g.

Ethyl 5-cyano-5-(2-cyanophenyl) valerate (II) : To a solution of potassium (2.5 g) in *tert*-butyl alcohol (125 ml), there was added a mixture of *o*-cyanobenzylcyanide¹ (10 g) and ethyl γ -bromobutyrate (13 g) dropwise during 30 min. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 hr. under perfectly anhydrous condition, and the solvent was then removed by distillation under reduced pressure. The resulting syrup was poured into water, the pH was adjusted to 4–5 with hydrochloric acid solution in cold and the solution was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residual liquid obtained on removal of ether was then percolated through a

4. R. B. Wagner and H. D. Zook, "Synthetic Organic Chemistry", John Wiley and Sons Inc., New York, 1953, p. 456.
5. L. Henry, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1886, **46**, 65.
6. I. Heilbron and H. M. Bunbury, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", Eyre and Spottiswode Ltd., London, 1946, p. 280.
7. A. W. D. Avison and A. L. Morrison, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 1471.

column of neutral alumina. The initial fractions, eluted from the column contained traces of starting materials. These were quickly followed by fractions containing a pale yellow syrup (4.5 g). This material was kept in the refrigerator for several days but could not be induced to crystallize. (Found : N, 10.83. $C_{15}H_{16}N_2O_2$ requires 10.90%).

Cyclisation of the Dinitrile (II) : Formation of Ethyl 1-bromo-3-amino-isoquinoline-4-butyrate (III). The above dinitrile (II; 4.5 g.) was dissolved in dry ether (100 ml) and cooled in an ice bath. Dry hydrogen bromide was then bubbled through the mixture for 2 hr, until the precipitation of the hydrogen halide salt appeared complete. The total reaction mixture was poured slowly into sodium bicarbonate solution. The solid product thus separated was filtered and washed with cold water which was finally crystallised from ethanol in light yellow micro-crystalline powder, yield 1 g, m.p. 222°. (Found : C, 53.21; H, 5.23; N, 7.98. $C_{15}H_{17}N_2O_2$ Br requires C, 53.4; H, 5.04; N, 8.31%).

The picrate was crystallised from ethanol in orange needles; m.p. 162°. (Found : N, 14.10; $C_{15}H_{17}N_2O_2$ Br, $2C_6H_3N_3O_7$ requires N, 14.08%).

Chloro compound of β -Ketopimelate (IV) and its condensation with benzylamine to convert it to (V) : β -Ketopimelate⁸ (4.5 g) was taken in dry chloroform (25 ml) and chlorine gas was passed through it at room temperature till the increase in weight was found to be about 1 g; kept for 1 hr. and then solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The compound thus obtained was dissolved in dry ether (25 ml) and to it was added under stirring a mixture of benzylamine (4 g) in dry ether (15 ml) at 5–10° during 1 hr. The reaction product was kept overnight on standing, diluted with water and the ethereal layer was separated and dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removal of ether a viscous material (3 g.) was obtained.

Cyclisation of (V) : Formation of Ethyl 3-carbethoxy-1,2-dihydroisoquinoline-4-butyrate (VI) : The above compound (V; 3 g) *in situ* was treated with concentrated sulphuric acid (9 ml) under stirring at 0–5° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The product was decomposed with little ice water, basified and extracted with ether and the ethereal extract was dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the ether the residue was kept in the refrigerator for 48 hr. The solid separated was filtered and crystallised from anhydrous ethanol in fine colourless needle shaped crystals (0.5 g.), m.p. 230°. (Found : C, 68.25; H, 7.31; N, 4.04. $C_{18}H_{23}NO_4$ requires C, 68.1; H, 7.20; N, 4.42%).

It afforded a yellow gummy picrate, which, however, could not be crystallised from common organic solvents to afford a pure sample for analysis. It gives carboxamate test for ester.